

DEVELOPMENT OF FUSION BONDING REPAIR OF THERMOPLASTIC RESIN COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The heating methods for fusion bonding repair of advanced thermoplastic composites were evaluated. Resistance heating and induction heating were considered to be the suitable heating methods for repair application. Resistance welding was applied to make patching type repair. Induction heating technique is developed for healing type repair. The heating pattern of composite laminates by induction heating was studied.

1. Introduction

Conventional repair methods for thermoset resin composites rely on adhesively bonded or mechanically fastened patches. These techniques may also be valid for thermoplastic systems. However, for the latter, there is a more natural approach to repair. Thermoplastics are resolidifiable and hence their composites should be repairable by fusion bonding techniques.

Fusion bonding is achieved by melting the mating surfaces and applying pressure to cause resin flow while cooling to the solidification temperature. Such a process can be utilized for various repairs such as restoring the integrity of a delaminated area or patching a puncture. Potentially, due to its simplicity, fusion bonding can be considered superior to conventional repair methods. The adhesion between the mating parts is achieved by self fusion of the matrix resin, thus eliminating any new moisture sensitive interface. In addition, fusion bonding is much faster compared to the cure cycle times of adhesives and hence more cost effective.

From the inventory of repair techniques, both resistance heating and induction heating are considered to be the most suitable methods for fusion bonding repair of thermoplastic composite.

In this paper, we present our recent results on fusion bonding repair of thermoplastic matrix composites.

2. Damage Modes and Repair Methods

The damage modes of thermoplastic systems are similar to those of

thermoset systems. Thus, from the viewpoint of repair, they can be put into two groups: matrix damage and fiber damage [1].

Matrix damage may be repaired under heat and pressure, a process similar to crack healing in polymers. For amorphous thermoplastics, healing can occur at a temperature above T_g . However, for crystalline thermoplastics, local remelting and resolidification are needed. "Thermal reforming" may be the more precise term for this process. Matrix damage is usually distributed throughout the laminate and hence for healing type repair, a volumetric heating pattern is preferred. Severe fiber damage needs to be repaired by patching. This process will resemble repairing thermoset composites, but the bonding can be achieved by self fusion bonding of the matrix resin. In this case, an interfacial heating pattern is desired where heat will be applied along the bondline but will not disturb other areas. The damage modes, repair methods and the desired heating methods are summarized in Figure 1.

Heating can be achieved either by external heating or by internal heat generation, as shown in Figure 2. In the case of volumetric heating, the heating rate of external heating methods is controlled by the thermal conductivity of the laminate, which is not high, especially in the direction transverse to the fibers. External heating is, therefore, a relatively slow process. On the other hand, internal heat generation is a quick and uniform heating method. In graphite or carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites, the electrically conductive fibers are in-situ heating sources. If current is introduced through the fibers, they will heat up the bulk material quickly and uniformly. Interfacial heating can be obtained by either surface heating or embedded surface heating. In the case of surface heating, two mating surfaces should be heated uniformly and then brought together quickly. This process may be easily realized on a production line, but it will be difficult to achieve in repair, where work is more manual. Therefore, so called embedded surface heating is the preferred technique.

Methods for fusion bonding of thermoplastic resin composites have been researched by many groups, and include: ultrasonic welding, vibration welding, focused infrared (IR) heating, induction heating, resistance heating hot tools [1-6]. The heating patterns of these methods differ considerably, Table 1, and hence their potential usefulness for repair can vary too, Table 2.

TABLE 1 HEATING METHODS FOR GRAPHITE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

method	volumetric heating	surface heating	embedded surface heating
hot tool	yes	yes	no
IR	yes	yes	no
laser	no	yes	no
resistance	no	yes	yes
induction	yes	yes	yes
ultrasonic	no	yes	yes
vibration	no	yes	yes

TABLE 2 EVALUATION OF HEATING METHODS

method	comment
<u>volumetric heating</u>	
hot tool, hot air, IR	flexible, but relatively slow heat affected zone
induction	uniform through thickness, quick (1 min)
<u>embedded surface heating</u>	
resistance	flexible, quick (1-2min) rectangular shape only
induction	quick (seconds) potential light equipment
ultrasonic, vibration	very quick (seconds) heavy equipment

For volumetric heating, hot plate, hot air and IR are external heating methods. These are slow processes and may produce a significant heat affected zone which could damage the local material properties of semi-crystalline thermoplastics [7]. For embedded surface heating, ultrasonic and vibration are based on the mechanism of vibration and the machinery may be quite heavy for repair applications. Therefore, at the present time, we selected induction heating for healing type repair and resistance and induction heating for patching repair.

3. Resistance Welding

By passing current through a conductive heating element sandwiched between two mating laminates, heat generated in the heating element will melt the matrix resin and thus create a fusion bond.

A process for joining thermoplastic resin composite by resistance welding was developed with the aid of numerical thermal analysis [8]. Once optimized, the technique produced a lap shear strength of 33.3 ± 4.2 MPa on APC-2 (PEEK) cross-ply laminates. This high lap shear strength was also retained after hot-wet conditioning of the composite material.

Patching type repairs by resistance welding have been studied using APC-2 composite. Four one-sided patch repairs have been made. The parent panels were 8-ply cross-ply laminate with the dimensions of 150x46x1.08mm. The patches were 4-ply unidirectional laminate with the dimensions of 46x46x0.54mm. Patches were laid with fibers aligned along the loading axis of the panels. Figure 3 shows the front view of a patched panel.

4. Induction Heating

Induction heating utilizes eddy currents to heat a conductor. However, for anisotropic conductive laminates, peculiar induction heating effects occur in composite materials.

4.1. The apparent conductivity

The conductivity of a general laminate can be estimated from the conductivity of a single layer of prepreg. For a single layer of prepreg, the conductivity varies with the off-axis angle θ as

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \sigma_0 \cos^2 \theta \quad (1)$$

where σ_0 is the conductivity along the fiber direction. The conductivity of a general laminate is then given by

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{l} \sigma_0 \sum_i \cos^2 \theta_i l_i \quad (2)$$

where $l = \sum l_i$; θ_i and l_i are the off-axis angle and the thickness of the i th-ply, respectively. It was found that in term of the electrical conductivity, not only the [0/90/+45/-45] and [-60/0/60] laminates but also the [0/90] laminate behave like a quasi-isotropic material.

The conductivity of APC-2 prepreg along the fiber direction was measured to be about $4 \times 10^2 / \Omega\text{-cm}$. The quasi-isotropic APC-2 laminates therefore have a conductivity of $2 \times 10^7 / \Omega\text{-cm}$.

4.2. The magnetic field of pancake coils

Pancake shaped coils were used for induction heating of composite laminates. The pancake coil can be considered as a series of rings, Figure 4. This simplification enables us to estimate the magnetic field produced by the coil from an analytical solution.

The magnetic field produced by a ring current I (Figure 5) is given by [9,10]

$$B = \frac{1}{4} \mu_0 I \frac{R^2}{(r^2 + R^2)^{3/2}} (2\hat{r}\cos\theta - \hat{\theta}\sin\theta \frac{2R^2 - r^2}{r^2 + R^2}) \quad (3)$$

where μ_0 is the permeability of vacuum ($\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{H/m}$).

The magnetic field in the work piece is dominated by that of the coil and the effect of the induced current is secondary [6]. Therefore, the field in the work piece produced by a current ring can be approximated by Equation 3. The field produced by a pancake coil is further approximated by summing the contribution of the individual rings:

$$B = \sum_i B(R_i) \quad (4)$$

The distribution of the B_z of a pancake coil was plotted in Figure 6. The coil contained two layers with six rings in each layer. The radius of the six rings were: 9.5, 15, 21, 25.5, 31 and 37mm, respectively. The distance between the two layers was about 7.2mm. In Figure 6, r' is the radial

distance in xy plane and R is the radius of the most outside ring. B_z was calculated for four z/R values; curves 1 to 4 correspond to z/R=0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, respectively.

The heat generated by an eddy current in a thin isotropic work piece which is placed parallel to the pancake coil was calculated and plotted in Figure 7. The figure suggests that, for a work piece which is much larger than the coil, the heating path is a circular annulus. This prediction agrees with that reported by other researchers [6]. However, the heating area is not strictly limited by the size of the coil. On increasing distance between work piece and coil, the heating annulus extends and moves outward. However, the heating intensity reduces rapidly with increasing distance. This phenomenon was observed experimentally, as will be discussed later.

4.3. Experimental observations

The induction heating of composites was also studied experimentally. Mask tape was used to cover the surface of the composites in order to observe the heating pattern. A fine thermocouple of 0.1mm diameter was also attached at one point to read the local temperature.

The experimental work was conducted on APC-2 laminates and PEEK/carbon fiber fabrics. The fabric was TPC 3K/PEEK by J.B.Martin and contained cross-laid fiber threads. The induction heating was conducted by using an Ameritherm 7.5KW unit at a working frequency of 160 KHz.

Figure 8a and 8b show the heating patterns in composite fabric specimens which were larger than the size of the coil. The electrical quasi-isotropic composite material displays a circular annulus pattern which resembles those of isotropic materials according to the analysis. In Figure 8 the inner and the outer circles of the heating annulus for the piece with z/R=0.1 are obviously smaller than those of the piece with z/R=0.45. This agrees with the prediction in Figure 7 such that the heating annulus extends outward when the work piece moves farther from the coil.

For the composite specimens whose sizes are smaller than that of the coil, the heating patterns are more complicated. Due to the mirror image nature, the eddy current induced by a pancake coil tends to flow a circular loop. However, the current also tends to follow the loop where the electrical resistance is the smallest, namely along the fibers in composite materials. In addition, there is an edge effect such that the current density is higher along a narrower path. It was found that the heating pattern is primarily determined by these three factors.

Figures 9a, 9b and 9c show the heating patterns of a round, a square and a rectangular composite fabric material, respectively. Both round and square pieces produced a square annulus heating pattern. In such cases, the eddy currents flow along a maximum available loop where fibers form a continuous path. Therefore, a square loop rather than a circular one was generated even though the work piece was round. For the rectangular piece, the edge effect is the controlling factor for the heating pattern.

4.4. Repair by induction heating

Healing type repair was demonstrated on APC-2 cross-ply laminate. Severely

delaminated and warped panels were vacuum bagged and resolidified under a pancake induction coil. The repair removed warped region and returned the panel to its original flat shape. A low pressure of about 0.9 atm was apparently sufficient to restore the integrity of the panels. At the present stage, mechanical testing has not been accomplished. Therefore no comment can be given regarding the mechanical properties.

5. Summary

Resistance welding and induction heating techniques were developed for repair of thermoplastic resin composites. Resistance welding may be applied for patching type repair while induction heating is certainly applicable to healing type repair. The heating patterns of composite laminates by induction heating was investigated. It was shown that the heating patterns of large pieces of quasi-isotropic composite materials caused by pancake coils can be predicted by an analytical approach. Composite pieces whose sizes are smaller than that of the coil showed more complicated heating patterns. Experimental work revealed that the heating pattern is primarily determined by three factors, namely the mirror image nature of the eddy current, the most conductive path and the edge effect.

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<u>Damage Mode</u>	<u>Repair</u>	<u>Heating Pattern</u>
Matrix Damage	healing (thermal reforming)	volumetric heating
fiber damage	patching	interfacial heating

Figure 1 Damage modes and repair techniques for thermoplastic composites.

Volumetric Heating

- external heating

- internal heating

Interfacial Heating

- surface heating

- embedded surface heating

Figure 2 Heating patterns and heating methods.

Figure 3 One side patched APC-2 laminate panel made by resistance welding.

Figure 4 Schematic of a pancake coil.

Figure 5 Field of a current ring. A current I flows on a ring of radius R lying in the xy plane.

Figure 6 The magnetic field distribution vs. the radial distance for a pancake coil which contains two layers with six rings in each layer.

Figure 7 The heat intensity distribution in a thin isotropic work piece lying parallel to a pancake coil.

Figure 8 The heating patterns on PEEK/carbon fiber fabric.
a) $z/R=0.1$, $I=11A$, $t=20s$; b) $z/R=0.45$, $I=19A$, $t=20s$.

Figure 9 The heating patterns on small pieces of PEEK/carbon fabric. $z/R=0.1$, $I=11A$, $t=20s$.